

CARBON FIBRE FROM VICTORIAN LIGNITE

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1 General Introduction

Carbon fibre (CF), as a high value-added carbon material, is one of the strongest and lightweight materials available today. Its popularity against traditional materials such as steel and aluminium in aerospace, civil engineering, the military, automotive and sports equipment industries is increasing because of its high rigidity, tensile strength and chemical resistance combined with low weight.

Victorian lignite (VL), with its inherently low N, low S and low ash content, is arguably the cleanest coal in the world. It has lower levels of these 'impurities' even than most forms of biomass. Since impurities often become concentrated in the product materials, VL is, from this perspective, a near ideal naturally occurring precursor material for all sorts of carbon products. VL is also a very cheap precursor material by virtue of its massive accumulation in large deposits that are mined by open cut methods. Moreover, its significant resemblance to lignin makes it highly prospective as a CF precursor.

Current work is studying methods of obtaining a material suitable for producing CF from VL. Several precursors have been produced from VL, then subjected to electro-spinning and wet-spinning to make the raw fibres.

2 Materials and methods

Victorian Lignite (VL), typically from the Loy Yang mine, was used as the raw material. A variety of VL derivatives, referred to as VLE (Victorian Lignite Extract) were prepared as part of this study. Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) polymer was obtained from Japan Exlan company. VLE and PAN were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) solvent with different weight ratios to obtain a spinning dope. Fabrication

of fibres was carried out by electro-spinning and wet-spinning instruments. Surface morphology and mechanical properties of the fibres were investigated by SEM ZEISS SUPRA scanning electron microscopy and FAVIMAT+ instruments.

3 Results

Five different spinning dopes with 80, 70, 60 and 50% VLE in PAN were prepared. Figure 1 shows the optical images of a VLE sample together with SEM images of two different electro-spun samples. As shown in Figure 1, pure VLE sample cannot be spun into a fibre structure however, by adding 50% PAN into the spinning dope, uniform nano-fibres were formed on the collector.

In order to investigate possibility of spinning continuous micro-fibres for structural applications, spinning dopes with 5 and 10wt% VLE in PAN were prepared. Both samples were spun successfully and their tensile strength and modulus were measured.

The tensile strength and modulus of 5wt% VLE in PAN sample were 0.31 and 12.15GPa, respectively. The corresponding values for 100% PAN fibres are 0.39 and 11.03GPa, respectively. A challenge will be to increase the concentration of VLE in the resultant fibres.

3.3 Figures and Tables

4.0 Acknowledgements

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Fig. 1 Image of VLE sample and SEM on pure VLE and 50% blend with PAN electro-spun samples

Fig. 2 5wt% VLE in PAN wet-spun fibres